

Personality and Academic Performance: A study of gender differences among STEM students at the University of Bath

Economics Undergraduate Final Year Research Project

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Abstract

While past research presents a strong relationship between personality and academic success, the gender differences in this relationship and the low-level facets within the Big Five personality domains remain relatively unexplored. This paper fills the gap in the research by investigating the relationship between the Big Five facets and academic success at university level using experimental survey data. In line with previous research, we find females scored statistically higher than males on Agreeableness and Neuroticism. Students that scored higher in Conscientiousness and, interestingly, Neuroticism achieved higher grades. This research notably reveals that the low-level facets of Productiveness, and Emotional Volatility show a significant positive relationship with grades. Whereas the facet of Anxiety displays a negative effect on grades. In addition, the paper finds evidence of heterogenous effects by gender and degree of study on the relationship between the low-level personality traits and grades.

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1. Introduction

The relationship between academic performance of students and their personality types has been a researched topic of interest for many years. The majority of this research has used a Big Five Inventory as their measure of personality. The Big Five consists of Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism. Although there are different measures of personality, all questionnaires aim to measure these five personality types, and also possibly the facets within them. From previous studies, the strongest predictor of academic success has been found to be Conscientiousness (Chamorro-Premuzic and Furnham, 2003; Trapmann *et al*, 2007; Corazzini *et al*, 2021). Highly conscientious individuals are perceived as organised, responsible, and reliable, important traits for academic success. The other four personality traits, specifically Openness and Neuroticism, have also been found to be correlated with academic success, however with much more variation between studies, leaving inconclusive results on these traits (Nofhle and Robins, 2007; O'Connor and Paunonen, 2007; Trapmann *et al*, 2007). The low-level facets within the Big Five have been much less researched, with only a handful of papers finding facet level differences between genders (Gensowski *et al*, 2021) and relationships with performance (Nofhle and Robins, 2007).

Similarly, gender disparities, both in academic performance and personality traits, has been an interesting topic among researchers. Females have been seen to outperform their male counterparts in academic achievement across numerous disciplines (Pomerantz *et al*, 2002; Conger and Long, 2010). Furthermore, females tend to score higher in Neuroticism and Agreeableness, while males tend to score higher in Extraversion (Costa, Terracciano, and McCrae, 2001; Chapman *et al*, 2007). Combining these two areas has been less researched. However, certain papers have aimed to show that gender differences in personality traits may play a role in the disparities in their academic achievement (Khan, 2020; Olowookere *et al*, 2020).

Despite extensive research on academic outcomes and personality traits, very little research has focused on gender differences in the low-level facets or specifically in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths) programs. STEM programs have conventionally been male dominated. Wang and Degol (2016) attribute this to several

reasons, two being differences in occupational interest and lifestyle values. Therefore, female differences in personality traits are likely to contribute to the underrepresentation of females in STEM subjects. As females in our sample have chosen to enter male dominated fields, they may possess more similar personality traits than the general population of females would with males. This paper will investigate the extent of genders' personality differences in our sample.

This research paper will aim to fill this gap in the literature by examining the gender differences in the relationship between low-level personality traits and academic performance. Particularly, this paper intends to:

1. Identify the personality traits of female and male students in a sample from STEM programs at the University of Bath.
2. Examine the gender differences in personality traits, at both the domain and facet level.
3. Investigate the relationship between personality and academic performance and assess whether in this relationship there exists gender or, potentially, any other differences.

The study will employ quantitative data collection through an experimental survey. Personality traits will be measured using the Big Five Inventory-2 questionnaire (Soto and John, 2017), a relatively new, 60-item inventory for the Big Five personality traits, and three facets within each. These are outlined below (Cambridge University Press, 2023; Cherry, 2023).

Extroversion

A personality characterised by high energy, outgoingness, warmth, and a preference for engaging with others in a social manner. This personality type is associated with leadership behaviour and career choices.

Sociability: the tendency to seek out companionship and engage in social situations.

Assertiveness: being confident to say what you want and believe.

Energy level: being energetic, enthusiastic, and animated in daily activities.

Openness

A person with a highly open personality is characterised by high levels of imagination, creativeness, and open-mindedness. Highly open individuals are more willing to listen to a variety of opinions and are more open to trying new ways of doing things.

Intellectual curiosity: the desire to learn new things and dive deeper into the inner workings of a topic or subject.

Aesthetic sensitivity: the ability to appreciate beauty and judge artistic merit.

Creative imagination: the generation of new and unique ideas.

Agreeableness

Agreeableness describes an individual who tend to put others needs before their own, they are highly empathetic, trustworthy, and forgiving. These individuals may struggle with tough decisions and find it hard to assert their own needs.

Compassion: a feeling of deep sympathy and sorrow for another.

Respectfulness: showing admiration for someone or something.

Trust: believing that someone is good and honest, or that something is safe and reliable.

Conscientiousness

An individual who is highly conscientious is seen to be responsible, reliable, and hard working. They do not make careless or impulsive decisions but instead are more rationale and tend to work carefully and diligently to achieve their goals.

Organisation: able to plan or do things according to a system and keep things tidy.

Productiveness: able achieve a lot by working hard.

Responsibility: able to have control over something or someone, and be accountable for these things.

Neuroticism

Perceived as a negative personality trait characterised by a high level of anxiety or irritability, feelings of self-doubt and sadness. These individuals may become over stimulated and be unable to calm themselves down or manage feelings of worry.

Anxiety: a feeling of unease, such as fear or worry.

Depression: feelings of despondency and loss of pleasure or interest in activities.

Emotional Volatility: Emotions become intense and overwhelming, and can't be controlled for periods of time.

Academic performance will be measured using students' last year's academic grade, as a percentage between 0 and 100. Personal characteristic information will also be acquired through the survey design to be used in the analysis. The paper will then examine the differences in genders' grades and personality traits in the sample and assess whether there exist any correlations between these variables by running OLS (Ordinary Least Squares) regression analysis. Finally, the existence of heterogenous effects by personal characteristics will be examined to understand if the relationship between personality and academic success varies by gender, degree of study or family income.

The economic implication of academic performance is extensive and plays a large part in labour market decisions of students in their future working lives. A student who performs well in university will subsequently have the opportunity to apply to higher paid and more prestigious job in the workforce. Finding and understanding a relationship between these variables and academic performance could have many ripple-on effects in helping to reduce labour market disparities between genders. Moreover, the results could have positive implications for educational policy and practice. If certain traits are found to be a strong predictor of academic success, promoting the development of these personality traits at a young age could aim to improve academic outcomes for all.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. The next section reviews existing literature on the relationship between the Big Five and academic grades, as well as gender differences in personality traits and academic performance. Section 3 presents the experimental design and descriptive statistics of our sample. Section 4 covers the regression analysis and discusses the results obtained. Section 5 concludes.

2. Literature Review

The first part of this literature review will focus on research on the relationships between personality and academic performance.

Nofle and Robins's (2007) research is a very significant paper for this topic as they partly investigated the low-level facets as well as the Big Five. They aimed to investigate the relationship between the Big Five personality traits and academic outcomes. Primarily, the authors reviewed pre 2007 literature on the relationships between personality and academic performance. A summary of the findings from this is shown below.

Table 1. Nofle and Robins (2007) Literature Review Findings

Big Five	Percentage of papers that found a significant positive (+) or negative (–) effect on academic success
Conscientiousness	(+) 75%
Openness	(+) 25%
Agreeableness	(+) 15%
Neuroticism	(–) 20%
Extraversion	(+) 5%, (–) 15%

Though Conscientiousness was the best predictor of academic outcomes, it did greatly differ in magnitude across the studies. Nofle and Robins suggest this could be put down to the different facets embedded within the Conscientiousness domain, with some facets relating to academic performance more than others (Wolfe and Johnson, 1995; Paunonen and Ashton, 2001).

Nofle and Robins then conducted four experimental studies, collecting data on the Big Five personality traits, Grade Point Average (GPA) and SAT scores. They collected data using various inventories, including the 208-item HEXACO Personality Inventory, where facets were also covered. The sample size was very high; one of the four samples consisted of over 10,000 undergraduate students. They found Conscientiousness to be strongly associated with higher GPA regardless of which personality questionnaire was

used, and when controlling for gender. There was a weak significant correlation found between college GPA and Openness, which only held in 3 of the 4 samples, and disappeared when controlling for gender and SAT scores. They also found a weak positive relationship between Agreeableness and high school GPA and a weak negative relationship between Extraversion and college GPA, however, neither of these held throughout all four samples. They found that it was the achievement-striving, self-controlling, and persevering facets of Conscientiousness, and, interestingly, not the organizational aspect. Nofle and Robins's study provides robust evidence that personality traits, predominantly Conscientiousness and Openness, are strong predictors of successful academic grades. However, the authors warn that personality is just one of many factors that can contribute to academic success, and that other factors, such as study habits, and social support, play important roles in a student's level of academic success.

O'Connor and Paunonen's (2007) conducted secondary research in the form of a literature review on the Big Five personality traits as predictors of post-secondary academic performance. From their meta-analysis they found, as with Nofle and Robins (2007), that Conscientiousness was the most consistent and strongest predictor of academic success. They also found that the magnitude of the relationship between academic success and Conscientiousness greatly varied between studies. Of particular interest to this study, they also noted that specifically academic performance measured by undergraduate course final grades were found to be predicted by Conscientiousness in four papers, (Dollinger and Orf, 1991; Paunonen and Ashton 2001; Lounsbury *et al* 2003; Conard, 2006). Openness was found to have a positive relationship with academic performance in a few studies. However, they found a correlation of only $r = 0.06$, showing little evidence of a robust association between Openness and academic success. They put this down to possible unobserved moderator variables affecting if Openness influences academic performance. Poropat (2009) also conducted a thorough meta-analysis. They reported that Conscientiousness strongly predicts academic achievement, again adding to the literature that consistently highlights this.

The second part of this literature review will examine literature specifically on gender differences in both academic performance and personality traits, although separately. Pomerantz *et al* (2002) researched differences in grades at school level on a sample of

932 children and found females significantly outperformed males in each category. Investigating academic performance in a large public university in Turkey, D. Meltem *et al* (2007) aimed to see if there existed any significant gender differences between undergraduate students. Using cumulative grade point average, CGPA, as their measure of academic success and employing additional measures such as university entrance scores, they conducted multivariate analysis using various level effects. They found that females outperform their male counterparts, which also holds after controlling for field of study and individual attributes. Interestingly, when controlling for type of school attended before university, females didn't see any fall in their advantage over their male counterparts. Only male students enjoy a "grade premium" from attending a better type of school. These results suggest that female students make better use of their own endowments and take advantage of the opportunities offered by their university. Combining this study with research into the personality types of the students in this sample could have been an interesting extension on this research, and an area this paper itself will hope to cover. Furthermore, the study, as highlighted by D. Meltem *et al*, was based on a selected university in Turkey. Further study to see if the results can be generalized across other undergraduates would be beneficial. Other research has also drawn the same conclusions. Conger and Long (2010) investigated the gender gaps in college. They found that males score lower than females in their first semester of college. This gap only widens further after the first semester in terms of grades and credits achieved. This could be due to females having non-academic advantages such as peer and teacher expectations (Reynolds and Burge, 2004). And also, different non-cognitive skills to males (Jacob, 2002), such as higher levels of organisation and self-discipline, and ability to seek help from others; all relating to personality traits.

Research on gender differences within the Big Five personality traits has been explored in various papers. Costa *et al* (2001) showed that US women score higher than men in both Neuroticism and Agreeableness. McCrae *et al* (2005) replicated these findings in a study on college students from 50 different cultures. They again found that females tended to score higher than males in all facets within Neuroticism and Agreeableness. They found that gender differences varied in the other three trait's facets, with females scoring higher in some and males scoring higher in some facets within each domain, not giving a clear conclusion. This study shows robust results, though the authors note a limitation was that they mostly used college aged adults due to the sample convenience.

However, for relevance to this study on undergraduate students, this limitation is beneficial, where similar results could be expected. Chapman *et al* (2007) aimed to investigate whether these results also held in older samples of adults. They found that again, even in older samples, women scored higher in both Neuroticism and Agreeableness. This demonstrates the solidity of these gender differences even throughout our lifespans. Most recently, Gensowski *et al* (2021) applied the BFI-2 inventory, which is to be used in this research, to investigate the sub-facets within each of the Big Five. They found from a sample of over 100,000 individuals, that women scored higher than men in all 5 domains, and most facets, at almost every stage of the life-cycle. The largest differences between the genders were found in Agreeableness, driven by the facet of Compassion, Neuroticism, driven by Anxiety, and Conscientiousness, driven by Responsibility. When investigating differential effects by income, they find that people with higher income report higher levels of Conscientiousness, Agreeableness, Extraversion and Openness, and lower levels of Neuroticism.

Fewer papers have looked into the gender differences between personality traits and academic performance simultaneously. The final part of this literature review will explore papers conducting research in this area.

Dur Khan's (2020) paper, *Gender Differences in Personality Traits in Relation to Academic Performance*, aimed to understand the moderating effect of gender in defining a relationship between personality traits and gender. The author conducted secondary research in the form of a literature review and collected primary data on graduate students in Mumbai. Data was collected on 666 students from a sample size of over 10,000. The author asked questions on the Goldberg, Lewis Big-Five Scale (1992) and graduation percentage as the measure of academic performance. Firstly, differences in personality traits between genders were inspected. There was a significant difference in only Emotional Stability (Neuroticism) between male and females; females had lower Emotional Stability. Dur Khan then investigated how the personality traits affect the grades of students. Using Mann-Whitney analysis, it was found Extraversion and Agreeableness positively influenced academic performance, not Conscientiousness. This is incongruent with many other papers. However, when looking into the gender breakdown Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, and Emotional Stability

were significantly correlated to male graduation percentage. Whereas in females' Conscientiousness and Openness were significantly correlated to their graduation percentage. Conscientiousness was the only personality trait to significantly impact both female and male students' academic performance. This would suggest that Conscientiousness is a predictor of academic success for both males and females, yet the whole data set didn't find this result, creating some inconsistencies. This could be because data on personality is very noisy, and measurement error was picked up in the results.

Olowookere *et al* (2020), explored the effect of gender and personality on educational performance at a university in Ogun State, updating a previous study. This experimental study used the BFI-40 item inventory, consisting of 103 female, and 98 male participants. The academic performance of female students was higher than males. Females scored higher in Conscientiousness, and males scored higher in Extraversion. Conscientiousness was significantly positively related to academic performance, which concurs with past research. As they found that females scored higher in Conscientiousness, this could explain the finding that they also had higher grades. Their initial study also found that Neuroticism was negatively related to academic grades, which has also been found in other research (Chamorro-Premuzic and Furnham, 2003) creating some discrepancies as they found no relationship in this paper. As they state in their discussion, other papers have found no correlation between Neuroticism and grades, but have found statistically significant relationships between Anxiety and Impulsiveness, the facets within the Neuroticism domain. Further study into the facets within Neuroticism could have led to a significant result between these personality tendencies and academic outcomes.

Corazzini *et al* (2021) investigated the influence of personality traits on university performance on a sample of 3,242 students. They aimed to account for possible sources of heterogeneity and omitted variable bias in their OLS regression analysis. Specifically, they considered gender, age, school background and parental information as explanatory factors of academic outcome that could relate to personality. They found statistical differences in the density distributions of the Big Five for males and females in all the five traits except Openness. Furthermore, they concluded that higher levels of Openness and Conscientiousness had a significant positive impact on a student's

academic outcome. This regression analysis also included an interaction between the Big Five and a gender dummy variable to test for heterogeneity. The results of this suggested that the estimated effects on academic success are not heterogeneous between genders. This study shows robust results, however, lacks some of the depth into the personality traits by not including any low-level facets. Investigating the facet-level personality traits may have given a heterogeneous result in an interaction or confirmed the non-heterogeneous result even at the facet level.

From this review of the literature, it can be concluded that there is a paucity of research on gender differences in the relationship between academic performance and personality traits. Hence, as suggested by Olowookere *et al* (2020), this research will aim to investigate further into this less researched area and add to this body of knowledge. This paper then aims to further the scope of any investigation done previously, by specifically looking into the facets within the personality domains, a notable gap in the research done thus far.

2.1 Hypotheses

Based on the previous literature review the following hypothesis are defined:

Hypothesis 1: *Females obtain higher academic grades than their male counterparts.*

Hypothesis 2: *Female students score higher than males on Neuroticism and Agreeableness.*

Hypothesis 3: *Conscientiousness is positively associated with academic success.*

Only Conscientiousness has been considered in H3 due to the varying degree of results found on the other four traits. Nonetheless, all low-level traits' relationship with academic success will be investigated.

3. Experimental Design

3.1 Identification of variables

Academic performance

The dependent variable for this study is academic performance. This research uses students' average grade in their last academic university year as the measure of academic performance, given as a self-reported number between 0-100.

Personality traits

The main independent variable to be studied are personality traits. More specifically this study will investigate the Big Five personality traits: Extroversion, Openness, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness and Neuroticism, and the three facets within each. This has been done using the 60-item BFI-2 inventory presented by Soto and John (2017).

Other independent variables of notable relevance included in this study have been career aspirations, risk tolerance and cognitive ability of the individuals. Females in the sample cohort may be aiming for different career paths than their male counterparts, which could correlate with academic grades as students aim to work harder to fulfil these goals. Secondly, risk tolerance. A highly risk tolerant student may risk studying less for an exam, which could lead to a correlation between risk aversion and academic success. Thirdly, cognitive ability. A higher level of cognitive ability is, of course, expected to have a high correlation with grades regardless of gender. Alike Corazzini *et al* (2021), for individual level effects, a range of other variables that may affect student performance are considered. These include age, year of study, parental income, parental education, type of school attended between the ages of 14-18, individuals time spent playing sport and revising, individuals drinking and smoking habits.

3.2 Design

The design of the questionnaire incorporates each of the variables discussed above, consisting of five sections (see Appendix A for questionnaire). The first section contained questions on background information. The second section of the survey covered career aspirations, asking individuals to score from 1-5 their importance of a statement relating to their future career. This was done in a matrix format, where students select their chosen option; no typing is required (see Appendix A, Figure A1 for the matrix format). This was done where possible to reduce the effort required to complete the questionnaire, reducing the likelihood of incomplete responses. An average of these five answers was taken as the career aspirations score. The third section covered risk tolerance with the use of a single self-reflection risk aversion question in matrix table format. Respondents ranked their likeliness to take risk on a scale of 1-7, with 1 being not at all willing and 7 being very willing to take risk.

The next part was a cognitive reflection test, CRT, acting as a proxy for cognitive ability. Looking to include a cognitive ability test was an alternative, but these tests are very long and would have put the questionnaire in danger of not being completed. Therefore, the CRT was chosen to keep the length of the questionnaire down. This CRT consisted of three mathematical type problems which required a typed answer, no answer options were given (see Appendix A, Figure A2 for CRT questions and format). One point was given to each correct answer, allowing respondents to gain a score of either 0,1,2 or 3.

The final part of the survey was the BFI-2 60-item personality questionnaire presented by Soto and John (2017). The respondents are asked to rate to what extent each item is self-descriptive, e.g. "I am someone who is outgoing, sociable". These were issued using the matrix table layout, allowing respondents to easily select an option between 1 and 5; 1 being disagree strongly and 5 being agree strongly. The measures of the Big Five and their facets were obtained from recoding the reverse-scored items, and then averaging the scores of the questions that correspond with each trait. See Appendix A, Table A1 for BFI-2 questions and corresponding traits.

3.3 Data Collection

The data collection in this research has been carried out at the University of Bath. The target population was second, third and fourth-year undergraduate students and masters and PhD students at the University of Bath. First years were excluded because the measure of academic performance was the last academic years average, therefore at least one year of university had to be completed. The questionnaire was distributed electronically via Qualtrics, responses were recorded anonymously, and consent was obtained by all participants.

3.4 Descriptive Statistics

The total sample size was 112; 68 males, 42 females, and 2 other gender identities. The 2 other gender identities were removed from the sample due to the lack of responses and aim of the study to look specifically into male and female differences. This left a total sample size of 110 students, 68 male and 42 female.

This sample consisted of a range of STEM disciplines. Subsequently in the paper these are split into traditional-STEM (STEM), which in our sample consists of engineering and physics, and non-traditional-STEM (non-STEM), in our sample economics, psychology, social sciences. The sample contained 45 STEM and 65 non-STEM responses. The year of study ranged from second years through to PhD level, but the majority of responses were undergraduate students; 15/110 being postgraduate. The full sample characteristics can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Summary Statistics

Variable	Mean <i>N=110</i>	Standard Deviation <i>N=110</i>
Academic Grade	65.74	7.517
Female	0.382	0.488
Age	21.38	3.256
Smoker	0.118	0.324
Career Aspirations	3.855	0.839

Risk Aversion	4.118	1.332
Cognitive Ability	2.191	0.934
STEM	0.364	0.483
High Income	0.573	0.497
Mothers' Education; Less than University	0.300	0.460
Fathers Education; Less than University	0.264	0.443
<i>Big Five</i>		
Extraversion	3.213	0.761
Agreeableness	3.515	0.611
Conscientiousness	3.440	0.660
Neuroticism	2.886	0.841
Openness	3.635	0.544

This is expanded and broken down further into female and male to easily compare their characteristics in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Summary Statistics by Gender

Variable	Female Mean <i>N</i> =42	Female SD <i>N</i> =42	Male Mean <i>N</i> =68	Male SD <i>N</i> =68
Academic Grade	66.45	7.929	65.30	7.280
Age	21.02	1.456	21.60	3.978
Second Year	0.310	0.468	0.441	0.500
Third Year	0.405	0.497	0.235	0.427
Fourth Year	0.095	0.297	0.206	0.407
Masters	0.167	0.377	0.103	0.306
PhD	0.024	0.154	0.015	0.121
Study Time (High)	0.833	0.377	0.647	0.481
Exercise Time (High)	0.357	0.485	0.721	0.452
Alcohol (High)	0.500	0.506	0.515	0.503
Smoker	0.071	0.261	0.147	0.357
Career Aspirations	4.101	0.625	3.702	0.905
Risk Tolerance	3.810	1.042	4.309	1.458
Cognitive Ability	2.119	0.968	2.235	0.916

STEM	0.310	0.468	0.397	0.493
<i>Family Background</i>				
Ethnicity- White	0.738	0.445	0.809	0.396
Ethnicity- Black	0.071	0.261	0.000	0.000
Ethnicity- Asian	0.143	0.354	0.132	0.341
Ethnicity- Mixed	0.048	0.216	0.044	0.207
Ethnicity- Other	0.000	0.000	0.015	0.121
Private School	0.476	0.505	0.324	0.471
Grammar School	0.119	0.328	0.162	0.371
State School	0.405	0.497	0.515	0.503
High Income	0.619	0.492	0.544	0.502
Mothers' Education; Less than University	0.333	0.477	0.279	0.452
Fathers' Education; Less than University	0.262	0.445	0.265	0.444
<i>Big Five</i>				
Extraversion	3.292	0.710	3.164	0.792
Agreeableness	3.663	0.626	3.424	0.588
Conscientiousness	3.490	0.593	3.409	0.700
Neuroticism	3.236	0.808	2.670	0.791
Openness	3.595	0.546	3.659	0.544
<i>Big Five Facets</i>				
Sociability	3.232	0.960	2.930	1.060
Assertiveness	3.143	0.972	3.166	0.872
Energy Level	3.500	0.632	3.397	0.843
Compassion	3.792	0.894	3.430	0.810
Respectfulness	4.083	0.517	3.871	0.634
Trust	3.113	0.838	2.971	0.799
Organisation	3.649	0.841	3.654	0.896
Productiveness	3.185	0.796	3.279	0.854
Responsibility	3.637	0.644	3.294	0.791
Anxiety	3.708	0.864	3.066	0.973
Depression	2.911	0.975	2.599	0.917

Emotional Volatility	3.089	0.883	2.346	0.856
Intellectual Curiosity	3.845	0.669	4.022	0.656
Aesthetic Sensitivity	3.458	0.718	3.320	0.885
Creative Imagination	3.482	0.778	3.636	0.720

Income is classed as high if the respondent reported their family income when growing up a score of 5 or above on the scale of 1-7. Parental education is classed as low if they did not attend University or above, i.e. only have education up to A-level or equivalent. Study and Exercise time are classed as high if respondents reported that they spent over 4 hours per week on this. Alcohol consumption is classed as high if respondents reported they consumed over 4 units of alcohol per week. STEM refers to participants who study the classical stem subjects rather than non-traditional.

The average academic grade for females, 66.45%, was higher than their male counterparts, 65.30%. The median for females was also higher at 67%, compared to 66% for males. Study time is slightly higher for females and exercise time is lower, suggesting a reason for females scoring higher than males. However, the difference was not significant ($p\ value = 0.438$). Therefore, although females in the sample do score higher on average than males, there is not sufficient evidence to support H1. Amount of alcohol drunk or being a smoker also didn't statistically vary between genders. About 40% of males and 31% of females did STEM, but no significant differences were found ($p\ value = 0.358$).

Risk tolerance for males was significantly higher than females at the 10% level ($p\ value = 0.0558 < 0.100$). It has been seen that women tend to be more risk adverse than males (Charness and Gneezy, 2012; Nelson, 2012). Career aspirations, interestingly, was significantly higher at the 5% level for females than males ($p\ value = 0.0136 < 0.050$). This has had mixed results in past research, with some studies finding a significant differences between genders career aspirations (Nduta, 2020) and others finding none (York, 2008).

4. Results and Analysis

This section presents the results found for the Big Five and the low-level facets.

Following this, we investigate whether the relationship between academic success and personality traits is heterogeneous across gender, degree of study and income. To test for heterogeneity, we interact the Big Five and their facets with these personal

characteristics. All specifications, apart from the first columns of the baseline results for the Big Five and the facets, control for income and age.

Before estimating the regression. The variables were tested for correlations to ensure that variables used were independent, to minimise multicollinearity in the regression. When testing for correlations between variables it was found that there was a positive correlation between income and type of school attended (0.491), mothers' education (0.323), and fathers' education (0.476). As you'd expect, year of study and age was also highly correlated (0.623). Therefore, only income and age were included as controls in the regression.

Study time was found to be positively correlated to Conscientiousness; therefore, this was not included in the regression. Smoking was negatively correlated with both Conscientiousness and Agreeableness. Alcohol consumption was positively correlated with Extraversion and exercise time was correlated with risk aversion. Therefore, for personal characteristics, these correlated variables were removed, leaving gender, cognitive ability, risk tolerance, career aspirations, to be ran in the regression. Full correlation matrix in Appendix B, Figure B1.

4.1 Baseline Results

4.1.1 Big Five Results

The research estimate the following specification by ordinary least squares (OLS):

$$Y_i = \alpha + \sum_{k=1}^5 \beta_k score_{ki} + \gamma X_i + \delta Z_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

Where Y_i is the measure of academic performance, $k = 1, \dots, 5$ are each of the Big Five personality traits, X_i are personal characteristics (gender, cognitive ability, risk tolerance, career aspirations, traditional-STEM), and Z_i is a vector for additional controls used (age and income).

Table 4. Big Five Personality Traits and Grades (OLS)

y = academic grade	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
<i>Big Five</i>								
Extraversion	- 0.458 (0.808)	- 0.612 (0.804)	- 0.666 (0.840)	-0.222 (0.861)	- 0.613 (0.845)	- 0.954 (0.939)	- 0.619 (0.856)	- 0.441 (0.961)
Agreeableness	0.017 (0.778)	0.292 (0.781)	0.257 (0.799)	0.419 (0.793)	0.297 (0.802)	0.355 (0.813)	0.251 (0.802)	0.602 (0.813)
Conscientiousness	2.023** (0.831)	1.825** (2.202)	1.817** (0.834)	1.794** (0.823)	1.822** (0.835)	1.767** (0.839)	1.860** (0.848)	1.821** (0.840)
Neuroticism	1.482 * (0.801)	1.520 * (0.798)	1.431 (0.888)	1.612 * (0.881)	1.432 (0.890)	1.538 * (0.903)	1.451 (0.894)	1.824** (0.905)
Openness	0.436 (0.750)	0.453 (0.781)	0.486 (0.758)	0.291 (0.755)	0.560 (0.766)	0.449 (0.762)	0.512 (0.765)	0.360 (0.771)
Female			0.377 (1.627)	0.422 (1.606)	0.423 (1.632)	0.555 (1.651)	0.477 (1.662)	0.953 (1.671)
STEM				2.971 * (1.549)				3.210** (1.581)
Cognitive Ability					0.582 (0.766)			0.630 (0.766)
Risk Tolerance						0.460 (0.662)		0.665 (0.663)
Career Aspirations							- 0.303 (0.917)	-0.667 (0.920)
Income		/	/	1.174** (0.588)	/	/	/	1.311** (0.605)
Age		/	/	0.403 * (0.218)	/	/	/	0.387 * (0.220)
<i>N</i>	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
R^2	0.098	0.138	0.138	0.169	0.143	0.142	0.139	0.185
F-stat	2.262	2.328	2.025	2.256	1.856	1.844	1.796	1.831

*** denotes significance at the 1% level, ** at 5% and * at 10%. The Big Five variables have been standardised to have a mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1. All regressions, apart from the baseline results of (1), control for age and income, where estimates were added if significant.

Table 4 above reports the estimation results of the effects of the Big Five personality traits on academic grades. The stability of the estimated parameters on the Big Five traits can be evaluated by comparing results after adding in personal characteristics and additional controls. Conscientiousness and Neuroticism exhibit statistically significant positive coefficients, which remains after controlling for age and income, column (2). Conscientiousness is particularly robust to the inclusion of all the control variables, staying at 5% significance throughout each regression. The statistically positive effect of Conscientiousness is consistent with the literature and an expected result (H3). Neuroticism's significance is lost with the inclusive of female as a dummy variable. However, this personality trait becomes the most intensive positive effect on the inclusion of all the control variables, column (8). This is an interesting result. The literature discussed above finds that Neuroticism either has no (Nofle and Robins, 2007) or a negative effect (Furnham, 2003) on grades. Further investigation into the facets of Neuroticism may allow for more detailed conclusions to be drawn here.

The inclusion of all variables in column (8) report that studying a traditional STEM subject has a significant positive effect on academic grades. Income and age also both positively effect academic grades. This significant result for income has been seen in past research. Research on school level academic success find that lower income is associated with lower grades (Morrissey *et al*, 2014), and higher family socioeconomic status helps students obtain higher grades (Qi, 2022).

4.1.2 Facet Level Results

We estimate the following specification by ordinary least squares (OLS):

$$Y_i = \alpha + \sum_{k=1}^{15} \beta_k score_{ki} + \gamma X_i + \delta Z_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

Where Y_i is the measure of academic performance, $k = 1, \dots, 15$ are each of the 15 facets within the Big Five, X_i are personal characteristics (gender, traditional-STEM, cognitive ability, risk tolerance, career aspirations), and Z_i is a vector for additional controls used (age and income).

Table 5. Facet Personality Traits and Grades (OLS)

<i>y = academic grade</i>	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
<i>Big Five Facets</i>				
<i>Extraversion</i>				
Sociability	-1.081 (1.060)	-1.247 (1.021)	-1.354 (1.053)	-0.770 (1.079)
Assertiveness	-0.253 (1.109)	-0.349 (1.021)	-0.297 (1.091)	-0.241 (1.108)
Energy level	1.225 (0.966)	1.418 (0.932)	1.373 (0.942)	1.327 (0.963)
<i>Agreeableness</i>				
Compassion	-1.333 (0.920)	-1.088 (0.905)	-1.098 (0.910)	-1.013 (0.988)
Respectfulness	1.575 * (0.918)	1.434 (0.882)	1.377 (0.895)	1.518 (0.892)
Trust	-0.296 (0.847)	-0.156 (0.819)	-0.136 (0.824)	-0.037 (0.813)
<i>Conscientiousness</i>				
Organisation	0.590 (0.958)	0.428 (0.929)	0.457 (0.935)	0.378 (0.921)
Responsibility	-0.631 (0.934)	-0.565 (0.906)	-0.689 (0.951)	-0.871 (0.963)
Productiveness	2.229 ** (0.921)	2.172 ** (0.891)	2.251 ** (0.912)	2.781 *** (0.949)
<i>Neuroticism</i>				
Emotional Volatility	2.586 ** (1.137)	2.569 ** (1.119)	2.373 * (1.207)	2.367 * (1.221)
Anxiety	-2.090 ** (1.0459)	-2.001 * (1.019)	-2.083 ** (1.041)	-1.843 * (1.028)
Depression	1.401 (1.157)	1.431 (1.128)	1.521 (1.151)	1.632 (1.173)
<i>Openness</i>				
Intellectual Curiosity	-0.627	-0.536	-0.493	-0.690

	(0.775)	(0.750)	(0.759)	(0.767)
Aesthetic Sensitivity	1.256	1.191	1.189	1.245
	(0.793)	(0.770)	(0.774)	(0.775)
Creative Imagination	-0.406	-0.517	-0.506	-0.241
	(0.796)	(0.784)	(0.788)	(0.795)
Income		0.938 *	0.931 *	1.299 **
		(0.555)	(0.558)	(0.564)
Female			0.775	1.565
			(1.742)	(1.775)
STEM				3.103 **
				(1.520)
Cognitive Ability				0.891
				(0.740)
Risk Tolerance				0.205
				(0.674)
Career Aspirations				-1.446
				(0.944)
<i>N</i>	110	110	110	110
<i>R</i> ²	0.280	0.318	0.320	0.372
<i>F – stat</i>	2.354	2.525	2.375	2.340

*** denotes significance at the 1% level, ** at 5% and * at 10%. The personality variables have been standardised to have a mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1. All regressions, except for the baseline results of (1), control for age and income, income estimates were included due to their significance.

Table 5 presents the estimates of the effect of the 15 facets of the Big Five personality traits on academic grades. In the baseline estimates with no controls, column (1), Emotional Volatility and Anxiety exhibit statistically significant coefficients. Interestingly, Emotional Volatility positively effects grades and Anxiety negatively effects grades. Overall Neuroticism exhibits a positive coefficient in the Big Five regression (Table 4 above). Therefore, the positive effect of Emotional Volatility must be outweighing the negative Anxiety effect in Neuroticism. These results remain significant at the 10% level with the inclusion of the control and additional variables. Emotional Volatility has the larger effect, an increase in one standard deviation is

associated with a 2.4% increase in grades compared to a 1.8% fall in grades estimated from Anxiety.

Productiveness exhibits a statically significant positive effect on grades. This is the only facet within Conscientiousness that is significant, suggesting this is the main trait that is driving Conscientiousness's positive effect on grades. This differs from Nofhle and Robins (2007) who obtained achievement-striving, self-controlling, and persevering as the most relevant low-level facets. However, they used different BFI questions which contain different facet traits. This result holds on the inclusion of control and additional variables, reaching the 1% level, and is the largest effect of any of the facets on grades. An increase of a standard deviation in the level of Productivity is associated with an increase in grades of 2.8%. This is a higher increase in grades than Conscientiousness estimates (1.8% increase from Table 4 column (8)). This could be due to the facet of Responsibility within Conscientiousness, though not significant, displaying a negative coefficient, and so may be bringing down the estimate for Conscientiousness alone.

Respectfulness, within Agreeableness, exhibits a statistically significant positive effect on grades. However, this result does not hold on the inclusion of the control variables and additional personal characteristics. Though we did not see a significant effect from Openness, as other research has found that this domain positively effects grades (Nofhle and Robins, 2007), the facet level investigation may have given a result. However, no facets within Openness are significant.

4.2 Heterogeneous Effects

Personality traits may be correlated with academic grades differently by gender, degree of study or family income. This section will investigate whether these subgroups have differential effects of personality traits on academic performance.

4.2.1 Gender on the Big Five

In Section 4.1.1, we do not find any evidence that women and men's academic grades differ, with no significance being reported when including a female dummy for gender into the regression. When controlling for personality traits, the point estimates for being female is 0.377 (1.627), Table 4, column (3). Performing a regression with only academic grades regressed on gender without controls for personality traits, still delivers a highly non-significant result of 1.150 (1.1478).

However, there does exist some significant gender differences in the distributions of the Big Five personality traits. Figure 1 below suggests a difference in Neuroticism. Statistical tests confirm that women in the sample tend to be more neurotic (two sample t-test, $p < 0.001$) and are also more agreeable ($p = 0.046$). This is coherent with many studies looking at gender differences in personality traits (Costa *et al*, 2001; Chapman *et al*, 2007; Schmitt *et al*, 2008). Consequently, we test to see if the relationship between personality traits and academic grades differs for females and males.

The heterogenous effects are presenting in Table 6 below. Column (1) contains the baseline results, including controls for age and income, for easy comparison. Column (2) contains the interaction between the Big Five and the female dummy. This allows the effect of personality traits to vary between male and female. Interestingly, neuroticism which was statistically different between genders at the 1% level, does not appear to impact male and female academic grades very differently. Furthermore, no other traits seem to affect academic performance differently by gender. This is in line with results obtained by Corazzini *et al* (2021); they found that the estimated effects on academic success were not heterogeneous between women and men in their sample.

Figure 1. Personality Traits Density Distribution by Gender

Table 6. Big Five Personality Traits and Grades: Gender and Degree of Specification (OLS)

<i>y = academic grade</i>	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Extraversion	-0.612 (0.804)	0.315 (1.097)	-0.385 (0.987)	1.081 (1.337)
Extraversion x Female		- 2.610 (1.745)		- 3.070 * (1.813)
Extraversion x STEM			0.969 (1.827)	- 0.015 (1.961)
Agreeableness	0.292 (0.781)	0.833 (1.038)	0.543 (1.033)	0.385 (1.295)
Agreeableness x Female		- 1.562 (1.721)		- 0.767 (1.769)
Agreeableness x STEM			-0.481 (1.564)	- 0.443 (1.674)
Conscientiousness	1.825** (2.202)	2.222 ** (1.045)	0.303 (1.254)	1.230 (1.583)
Conscientiousness x Female		- 0.730 (1.912)		- 1.514 (1.994)
Conscientiousness x STEM			2.560 (1.652)	2.488 (1.808)
Neuroticism	1.520 * (0.798)	2.485 ** (1.191)	1.627 (0.988)	3.122 ** (1.360)
Neuroticism x Female		- 2.324 (1.835)		- 3.021 * (1.812)
Neuroticism x STEM			0.456 (1.621)	- 0.148 (1.710)
Openness	0.453 (0.781)	0.041 (1.034)	-0.535 (0.881)	- 1.092 (1.153)
Openness x Female		0.733 (1.596)		0.710 (1.591)
Openness x STEM			2.403 (1.635)	2.745 (1.700)
STEM			3.121 * (1.583)	/
Age	/	/	0.456 **	/

			(0.215)	
Income	/	/	1.220 **	/
			(0.586)	
<i>N</i>	110	110	110	110
<i>R</i> ²	0.138	0.176	0.230	0.213
F-stat	2.328	1.579	2.208	1.462

*** denotes significance at the 1% level, ** at 5% and * at 10%. The Big Five variables have been standardised to have a mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1. All regressions control for age and income of participants, income and age estimates have been added for significant results.

4.2.2 Degree of Study on the Big Five

There may also exist differences in the distribution of the Big Five personality traits by degree of study. Splitting the traditional STEM subjects such as Engineering and Sciences away from non-traditional STEM such as Economics and Psychology, Figure 2 below illustrates their different distributions. We find a statistically significant difference in Extraversion for STEM and non-STEM students at the 10% level using a two-sample t-test ($p\ value = 0.0668 < 0.1$). STEM students score lower in Extraversion than non-STEM students. There was not a significant difference between STEM and non-STEM for any of the other Big Five.

Column (3) in Table 6 presents the effects on grades when the results are allowed to vary by degree of study by introducing an interaction between the Big Five and STEM as a dummy variable in the regression. The omitted category is students who are studying for a degree in non-traditional STEM subjects. Interestingly, even with a significant difference in the distribution of Extraversion, these results show no significant differential effects for any of the Big Five traits by degree of study.

Although there are no heterogenous effects by degree of study, it may be possible that some differences in academic performance are driven by the gender composition of STEM students in our sample. When including an interaction for both gender and degree of study, shown in column (4), we can see the effects of the Big Five on grades

when they are allowed to vary by both gender and degree of study. There are significant results associated with Neuroticism. Neuroticism does not seem to affect females differently by degree of study, with no differential effects between females who do STEM or non-STEM degrees. However, there is a slight differential effect for males who do STEM or non-STEM, where an increase in Neuroticism of one standard deviation is associated with an increase in grades of around 3.12% for males who do not do STEM, but only around a 2.97% for males who do STEM.

Figure 2. Personality Traits Density Distribution by Degree of Study

4.2.3 Gender on Facets

We now look at any differences in the distribution of the 15 facets between genders. Statistical tests confirm that there exist statistical differences in six facets, two within Agreeableness, three within Neuroticism and one within Conscientiousness. Females in our sample tend to be more compassionate ($p = 0.031 < 0.05$), and respectful ($p = 0.071 < 0.10$), facets within Agreeableness. Females also tend to have higher levels of anxiety ($p < 0.01$), depression ($p = 0.094 < 0.10$), and emotional volatility ($p < 0.01$). Interestingly, females in our sample also tend to be more responsible ($p = 0.020 < 0.05$) than males. This supports Gensowski *et al* (2021), also finding facet-level gender differences in Compassion, Anxiety and Responsibility.

Finding these differences, we now explore whether the relationship between personality and academic performance differs between male and female by adding an interaction between the 15 facets and a female dummy variable for gender.

The heterogenous effects are presenting in Table 7 below. Column (1) contains the baseline results, including controls for age and income, for easy comparison. Column (2) contains the interaction between the facets and the female dummy. Interestingly, none of the facets which significantly vary between females and male appear to impact differently male and female grades. Respectfulness and Productiveness were the only two estimates to be significant and show heterogenous effects by gender. A one standard deviation increase in Respectfulness is estimated to increase grades for males by around 2%, whereas the effect is negligible (point estimate -0.012) for females, though this estimate interacted with female is not significant. A one standard deviation increase in Productiveness is estimated to increase grades for males by around 2.5%. This effect is different for females, with a one standard deviation increase associated with only around a 2% increase in grades, slighter lower than the effect for males, however again the productiveness interaction estimate is not significant.

Table 7. Facet Personality Traits and Grades: Gender and Degree of Specification (OLS)

<i>y = academic grade</i>	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
<i>Extraversion</i>				
Sociability	-1.247 (1.021)	-1.824 (1.470)	-0.947 (1.453)	- 1.138 (1.940)
Sociability x Female		2.069 (2.755)		1.295 (2.832)
Sociability x STEM			2.784 (2.515)	4.516 (2.873)
Assertiveness	-0.349 (1.021)	0.405 (1.689)	0.927 (1.433)	1.699 (1.983)
Assertiveness x Female		-1.958 (2.611)		- 0.866 (2.720)
Assertiveness x STEM			-3.628 (2.555)	- 6.747 ** (3.021)
Energy Level	1.418 (0.932)	1.418 (1.349)	0.046 (1.275)	-0.878 (1.892)
Energy Level x Female		-1.195 (2.299)		- 0.634 (2.448)
Energy Level x STEM			1.448 (2.256)	1.383 (2.692)
<i>Agreeableness</i>				
Compassion	-1.088 (0.905)	-1.068 (1.229)	-1.108 (1.307)	- 2.260 (1.698)
Compassion x Female		-1.256 (2.499)		- 0.499 (2.870)
Compassion x STEM			-0.622 (1.925)	1.069 (2.294)
Respectfulness	1.434 (0.882)	2.087 * (1.237)	1.525 (1.030)	2.431 (1.572)
Respectfulness x Female		- 2.099 (2.297)		- 3.078 (2.495)
Respectfulness x STEM			-0.889 (2.172)	- 0.630 (2.534)
Trust	-0.156 (0.819)	-0.276 (1.155)	0.427 (1.332)	0.222 (2.061)
Trust x Female		1.285		2.426

		(2.047)		(2.518)
Trust x STEM			-1.215 (1.782)	- 3.179 (2.308)
<i>Conscientiousness</i>				
Organisation	0.428 (0.929)	-0.098 (1.356)	1.017 (1.149)	0.567 (1.810)
Organisation x Female		2.158 (2.440)		2.822 (2.802)
Organisation x STEM			-0.334 (2.145)	- 0.096 (2.546)
Responsibility	-0.565 (0.906)	-0.402 (1.541)	-2.696 ** (1.323)	- 2.364 (2.079)
Responsibility x Female		-0.786 (2.381)		- 1.226 2.767
Responsibility x STEM			4.404 ** (2.067)	4.161 * (2.483)
Productiveness	2.172 ** (0.891)	2.438 * (1.276)	0.931 (1.133)	1.498 (1.811)
Productiveness x Female		-0.576 (2.444)		- 0.454 (2.844)
Productiveness x STEM			1.136 (2.035)	1.050 (2.765)
<i>Neuroticism</i>				
Emotional Volatility	2.569 ** (1.119)	2.886 (1.753)	2.745 * (1.531)	3.245 (1.981)
Emotional Volatility x Female		-0.974 (2.951)		- 5.509 (3.430)
Emotional Volatility x STEM			0.149 (2.410)	2.205 (3.285)
Anxiety	-2.001 * (1.019)	-1.830 (1.523)	-1.592 (1.348)	- 2.961 (2.093)
Anxiety x Female		-0.460 (2.963)		4.483 (3.364)
Anxiety x STEM			-2.466 (2.236)	-3.236 (2.654)
Depression	1.431 (1.128)	0.980 (1.643)	0.916 (1.395)	1.449 (2.228)

Depression x Female		0.321 (2.823)		- 0.482 (3.216)
Depression x STEM			1.831 (2.481)	0.575 (3.195)
<i>Openness</i>				
Intellectual Curiosity	-0.536 (0.750)	-0.915 (1.066)	-1.202 (0.902)	- 2.282 * (1.357)
Intellectual Curiosity x Female		1.145 (1.763)		1.866 (1.900)
Intellectual Curiosity x STEM			4.372 ** (2.125)	7.610 *** (2.719)
Aesthetic Sensitivity	1.191 (0.770)	0.790 (1.009)	0.702 (0.975)	0.752 (1.221)
Aesthetic Sensitivity x Female		0.681 (2.122)		0.594 (2.238)
Aesthetic Sensitivity x STEM			-0.069 (1.872)	- 1.202 (2.224)
Creative Imagination	-0.517 (0.784)	-0.373 (1.193)	-0.538 (1.070)	- 0.181 (1.660)
Creative Imagination x Female		0.172 (2.009)		-1.913 (2.311)
Creative Imagination x STEM			0.725 (1.699)	0.447 (2.170)
Income	0.938 * (0.555)	/	1.025 * (0.590)	/
STEM			2.676 * (1.556)	/
<i>N</i>	110	110	110	110
<i>R</i> ²	0.318	0.359	0.464	0.545
F-stat	2.525	1.290	1.996	1.464

*** denotes significance at the 1% level, ** at 5% and * at 10%. The Big Five variables have been standardised to have a mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1. All regressions control for age and income of participants, income estimates has been added due to the significance of the result in certain regressions.

4.2.4 Degree of Study on Facets

We now look at any differences in the distribution of the 15 facets between degree of study. Statistical tests confirm that there exist statistical differences in two facets within Extraversion. Non-STEM students in our sample tend to be more sociable ($p < 0.01$), and assertive ($p = 0.037 < 0.05$).

With these results in mind, we will again explore whether the relationship between personality and academic performance differs between STEM and non-STEM by adding an interaction between the 15 facets and a STEM dummy variable, Table 7, column (3). Interestingly, Sociability and Assertiveness both did not have any differential effects by degree of study on grades.

However, intriguingly, other traits seem to significantly affect academic grades differentially by degree of study. Increases in the level of Responsibility are positively correlated with grades for STEM degree students only. A rise in one standard deviation in Responsibility increases grades by around 2% for STEM students but is estimated to decrease grades by around 2.7% for non-STEM students.

There also exist differential effects of Intellectual Curiosity and Emotional Volatility by degree. Increased levels of Intellectual Curiosity and studying STEM is positively correlated with grades, while it is negatively correlated with grades for non-STEM students. A rise in one standard deviation in Intellectual Curiosity increases grades by around 3.2% for STEM students, at the 5% significance level. Whereas, for non-STEM students a rise in one standard deviation in Intellectual Curiosity decreases grades by around 1.2%, though this estimate is not significant. Emotional Volatility is positively correlated with grades for both STEM and non-STEM students, increasing grades by around 2.75% for non-STEM, at the 10% significance level. For STEM students this effect is slightly higher, at around a 2.9% grade increase for a one standard deviation increase in Emotional Volatility, although, this estimate is not significant.

Again, it may be the case that some of the differences are driven by the gender composition of STEM students in the sample. When including an interaction for both

gender and degree of study, Table 7, column (4), we see differential effects. Most notably Intellectual Curiosity shows differential effects. Studying STEM and being male is estimated to increase grades by 5.3%. Whereas studying non-STEM and being male is negatively correlated with grades, estimating a decrease in grades of 2.3% from one standard deviation increase in Intellectual Curiosity.

4.2.5 Family Background - Income

Finally, we look at family income as another characteristic that could affect the relationship between the personality traits and academic performance. Statistically, none of the Big Five density distributions for low-income vs high-income are significantly different from each other when testing using a two-sample t-test (density distribution graphs in Appendix B, Figure B1).

When including an interaction between the Big Five and a dummy for High Income we find no consistent evidence that students with higher income experience a different relation between the Big Five and academic success than those with lower income. (Appendix B, Table B2, Column (2)).

5. Concluding Remarks

This paper has presented research into gender differences in personality traits and how the Big Five and their low-level facets affect academic performance of male and female STEM students. In respect to our hypotheses, this research finds that females score significantly higher than males in both Agreeableness and Conscientiousness (H2). We find a robust relationship between Conscientiousness and academic grades (H3). These results both highly concur with past research. The sample does show that females obtain higher academic grades than males (H1), but this is not a significant difference.

This research also finds a positive relationship between Neuroticism and grades, contradictory to past findings. Within this domain, the facet of Emotional Volatility is driving this positive effect, while we find Anxiety negatively affects grades. Chamorro-

Premuzic and Furnham (2003) suggest that the negative association of Neuroticism with grades is driven by Anxiety, which our result supports. It is the facet of Emotional Volatility positively effecting grades which is the unusual result. No other research has found a similar result, exacerbated by minimal research on low-level traits. Further research on a larger sample size would be valuable to assess this result.

This paper also exclusively finds that the facet of Productiveness has a significant positive effect on grades. This develops past findings and allows for more accurate predictions of academic performance than the broad dimension alone (Corazzini *et al*, 2021).

The unique contribution of this paper comes from the low-level facet results, summarised above, and the differential effects by gender and degree of study. When looking at the interaction between personality traits and gender or degree of study, we find heterogenous effects. There are no differential effects found for the Big Five by gender or degree of study alone. However, when combining these, this research finds Neuroticism is correlated with academic grades differently for men and women who study STEM vs non-STEM. Furthermore, this research expands the findings further and shows that the facet-level personality traits do show differential effects by gender and degree of study. Specifically, we find heterogenous effects on academic performance by gender on Productiveness and Responsibility, heterogenous effects by degree of study on Responsibility, Emotional Volatility, and Intellectual Curiosity and heterogenous effects by gender and degree of study on Intellectual Curiosity.

5.1 External validity

Experimental research is often criticised regarding its external validity. This research has focused on University of Bath students, a top UK University. This would suggest individuals in our sample have different personality traits than the general population. Therefore, results found are more reflective of student populations only rather than over whole populations.

The accuracy of the personality scores may be undermined due to the self-reporting nature of the questionnaire and possibility of reference bias (Heckman *et al*, 2019). Males in the sample were significantly lower on Neuroticism than females, which, although is expected, may have been exaggerated by the fact that males report themselves to be lower on these questions than they are due to societal norms around males and emotions (Denkin, 2020). There may be a degree of ambiguity in any traits due to this. Yet, research in this area continue to use self-reporting questionnaires as the best way to obtain data on personality traits. Furthermore, the use of the BFI-2 has aimed to reduce the influence of acquiescent responding (Soto and John, 2017), hoping to reduce the limitations of a self-reporting questionnaire.

Additionally, respondents may not have been paying sufficient attention to the questions asked (Alvarez *et al*, 2019). However, only one response was excluded for clearly false responses of all 3s for the BFI-2 questions, suggesting that unserious engagement was low in our sample. As students chose to participate in this study knowing there was no incentive, for them to then not engage in the questions would be unlikely.

5.2 Implications

Roberts and DelVecchio (2000) found that personality is more impressionable in childhood and adolescence than in adulthood. Therefore, the findings of this study could be used by universities and educational bodies to foster the growth of personality traits which have positive effects on academic success in younger age groups. Specifically, from this papers' finding, the Productiveness facet within conscientiousness should be focused on being developed throughout adolescence and at university. As suggested by Corazzini *et al* (2021), this could be achieved by introducing compulsory attendance rules. Alternatively, to increase productivity, different lecture lengths could be adopted to be optimal for the highest levels of concentration from students. Universities could also use the knowledge that Anxiety and Emotional Volatility affect grades to provide additional support services and encourage openness about emotions among students. Similarly, our findings suggest

Anxiety negatively affected grades, and therefore Universities may want to introduce multiple exams or midterms throughout the year to reduce stress from one single final exam. The differential effects by degree of study and gender could also be used by universities to target specific groups when aiming to affect personality traits. For example, Intellectual curiosity had a positive effect on grades for STEM students, while a negative effect for non-STEM, therefore different policies should be used dependent on degree of study in some situations.

Suggested by Kyllonen *et al* (2005), universities could use the findings from this paper to aid university applicants in choosing an advantageous course for their personality type by looking at the applicants' personality profile and comparing this to successful graduates in that course. From this research for example, it was found that higher levels of Neuroticism in men that do non-STEM is associated with a larger increase in grades than those who do STEM. Therefore, if a male applicant is unsure on what subject area to enter and score high on Neuroticism, suggesting a non-STEM subject may result in a higher potential grade. However, before such a policy can be considered, further research should be done on larger sample sizes to corroborate these results.

Alike Corazzini *et al* (2021), these results can also support public investments in intervention programmes at school level with the aim to develop the favourable personality traits. The finding that Conscientiousness positively affects academic outcome highly concurs with past findings, therefore this domain and the Productiveness facet within this should be focused on at school level. Programmes in this area have been successful in creating positive changes in personality. Heckman *et al* (2019) presents evidence that targeted intervention efforts can positively effect personality, improve preferences and skills, referencing the Perry Preschool study and Project STAR. Bierman *et al* (2010) also find that well-implemented social-emotional learning programmes can have significant effects on academic engagement in junior school years.

5.3 Future Considerations

This research has focused on the low-level facets of the Big Five, a notable gap in the current research. Although the results do show significant and newly relevant findings, there are some areas where future research could focus. A larger sample size would allow for more reliable results, which this research struggled to obtain due to lack of funding and incentives for respondents. Future research would also benefit from a wider selection of subject groups. The STEM subjects in this sample were only from Engineering and Physics disciplines, missing out other sciences, maths, and computing subjects, and non-STEM subjects did not include any business or arts degrees; more dependable results may be found on their inclusion. Ultimately though, further research into the facet levels of the Big Five will validate this papers' findings and be beneficial to increase the literature on this under-researched topic.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Copy of consent form and questionnaire distributed to respondents:

Study Description:

Study Name: Personality and Performance

Description: We invite you to take part in a study which aims to gather information about personality traits and performance. If you agree to participate, you will be asked a series of questions about your background, academic performance and personality. Altogether, this should take around 10 minutes of your time. Participation in the study is completely voluntary. You are free to withdraw from the study at any time and you do not have to give a reason for doing so. You can do so by simply closing your browser or the window the experiment is in. This will erase all of your responses immediately. All data collected will be anonymous. Therefore, once you submit the survey it will no longer be possible to withdraw your data from the study. To take part in this study you must be over the age of 18. This study has received ethical approval by the ethics committee of the Department of Economics at the University of Bath.

If you have any questions about the study, please contact one of the researchers using the contact information below.

Duration: 10 Minutes

Researcher: Sophie Ketner, sk2377@bath.ac.uk

Principal Investigator: Dr Maria Cubel, mcs74@bath.ac.uk

Content Form:

Please select Yes, if you agree with the following statements:

- I confirm I am over the age of 18.
- I have received enough information about the project to make a decision about my participation.
- I understand that I am free to withdraw my consent to participate in the project at any time without having to give a reason for withdrawing.
- I understand the nature and purpose of the procedures involved in this project.
- I understand that the data collected is anonymous.
- I understand and acknowledge that the investigation is designed to promote scientific knowledge and that the University of Bath will use the data I provide only for the purpose(s) set out in the description of the study.
- I understand that my consent to use the data I provide is conditional upon the University complying with its duties and obligations under current data protection legislation.
- I hereby fully and freely consent to my participation in this project.

Demographics and Education, Section 1:

Q1. Please select your gender

- Male
- Female
- Any other gender identity

Q2. Please select an option which best represented your ethnic background

- White
- Black or Black British
- Asian or Asian British
- Arab
- Mixed or Multiple ethnic groups
- Other

Q3. Please enter your age

Q4. Please select your current year of study

- Second Year
- Third Year
- Fourth Year
- Masters Studies
- PhD Studies

Q5. Please enter the full title of your degree of study

Q6. Please enter your average academic grade for the previous year, as a % between 0 and 100

Q7. How much time do you spend doing university work/reading/revision outside of lectures per week?

- 0 hours
- 0-4 hours
- 4-8 hours
- 8-12 hours
- Over 12 hours

Q8. How much time do you spend exercising per week?

- 0 hours
- 0-4 hours
- 4-8 hours
- 8-12 hours
- Over 12 hours

Q9. How many units of alcohol do you drink per week?

- 0 units
- 0-4 units
- 4-8 units
- 8-12 units
- Over 12 units

Q10. Do you smoke?

- No
- Yes

Q11. What type of school did you attend between the ages of 14-18?

- Fee paying / private school
- Grammar school
- State school

Q12. Taking everything into account, how would you characterise the standard of living of the family in which you were born? If you think of a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means a poor family, 7 a rich family, and the other numbers are for the positions in-between, about where would you place the family you were born in?

Q13. What is the highest level of your mother's education?

- N/A
- GSCEs
- A-Levels
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's Degree
- Doctorate Degree

Q14. What is the highest level of your father's education?

- N/A
- GSCEs
- A-Levels
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's Degree
- Doctorate Degree

Career Aspiration, Section 2:

Q15. Please state how much you agree with the following statements on a scale of 1 to 5, with 5 being you strongly agree and 1 being you strongly disagree

- I want to be among the best in my field
- I want my work to have a lasting impact on my field
- I aspire to have my contributions to work recognised by my employer
- Being outstanding at what I do is very important to me

Risk Aversion, Section 3:

Q16. Are you a person who is fully prepared to take risk or do you try to avoid taking risk? Please tick a box on the scale, where 1 means "not at all willing to take risk" and the value 7 means "very willing to take risk"

Cognitive Reflection Test, Section 4:

Q17. If John can drink one barrel of water in 6 days, and Mary can drink one barrel of water in 12 days, how many days does it take them to drink one barrel of water together?

Q18. Jerry received both the 15th highest and the 15th lowest mark in the class. How many students are in the class?

Q19. A man buys a pig for £60, sells it for £70, buys it back for £80, and sells it finally for £90. How much has he made?

Personality Questions, BFI-2, Section 5:

Q20. Please write a number next to each statement to indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with that statement, using the following numbers; Disagree Strongly - 1, Disagree a little - 2 , Neither agree nor disagree - 3 , Agree a little - 4 , Agree strongly - 5

I see myself as someone who is...

(See Table A1 for statements)

End of Questionnaire:

We thank you for your time spent taking this survey. Your response has been recorded.

Please state how much you agree with the following statements on a scale of 1 to 5, with 5 being you strongly agree and 1 being you strongly disagree

	1- Strongly Disagree	2- Disagree a little	3 - Neither Agree nor Disagree	4- Agree a little	5- Strongly Agree
I want to be among the best in my field	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I want my work to have a lasting impact on my field	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I aspire to have my contributions to work recognised by my employer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Being outstanding at what I do is very important to me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure A1. Example of Matrix Question Format, using Career Aspiration Questions

If John can drink one barrel of water in 6 days, and Mary can drink one barrel of water in 12 days, how many days does it take them to drink one barrel of water together?

Jerry received both the 15th highest and the 15th lowest mark in the class. How many students are in the class?

A man buys a pig for £60, sells it for £70, buys it back for £80, and sells it finally for £90. How much has he made?

Figure A2. Cognitive Reflection Test Questions and Layout

Table A1. BFI-2 Personality Questions and Corresponding Personality Traits

Domain	Facet	I am someone who...
Extraversion	Sociability	Tends to be quiet Is talkative Is outgoing, sociable Is sometimes shy, introverted
	Assertiveness	Is dominant, acts as a leader Has an assertive personality Prefers to have others take charge Finds it hard to influence people
	Energy Level	Is full of energy Shows a lot of enthusiasm Rarely feels excited or eager Is less active than other people
Agreeableness	Compassion	Is compassionate, has a soft heart Can be cold and uncaring Is helpful and unselfish with others Feels little sympathy for others
	Respectfulness	Is respectful, treats others with respect Is polite, courteous to others Is sometimes rude to others Starts arguments with others
	Trust	Assumes the best about people Has a forgiving nature Tends to find fault with others Is suspicious of others' intentions

Conscientiousness	Organisation	Tends to be disorganized Is systematic, likes to keep things in order Keeps things neat and tidy Leaves a mess, doesn't clean up
	Productiveness	Is efficient, gets things done Is persistent, works until the task is finished Tends to be lazy
	Responsibility	Has difficulty getting started on tasks Can be somewhat careless Sometimes behaves irresponsibly Is reliable, can always be counted on Is dependable, steady
Neuroticism	Anxiety	Is relaxed, handles stress well Worries a lot Rarely feels anxious or afraid Can be tense
	Depression	Often feels sad Tends to feel depressed, blue Feels secure, comfortable with self Stays optimistic after experiencing a setback
	Emotional Volatility	Is emotionally stable, not easily upset Is temperamental, gets emotional easily Keeps their emotions under control Is moody, has up and down mood swings
Openness	Intellectual Curiosity	Has little interest in abstract Ideas Is complex, a deep thinker Avoids intellectual, philosophical discussions Is curious about many different things
	Aesthetic Sensitivity	Is fascinated by art, music, or literature Has few artistic interests Values art and beauty Thinks poetry and plays are boring
	Creative Imagination	Has little creativity Is inventive, finds clever ways to do things Is original, comes up with new Ideas Has difficulty imagining things

Appendix B

Table B1. Variable Correlation Matrix

	Age	Year	Grade	Study	Exercise	Alcohol	Smoke	School	Income	Med	Fed	Career	Risk	Cognitive	E	A	C	N	O
Age	1																		
Year	0.623	1																	
Grade	0.182	0.285	1																
Study	0.149	0.061	0.277	1															
Exercise	-0.083	-0.054	0.028	0.065	1														
Alcohol	-0.090	-0.085	-0.062	-0.126	0.215	1													
Smoke	0.019	0.052	-0.099	-0.217	-0.017	0.262	1												
School	0.138	0.002	-0.210	0.230	-0.038	-0.193	-0.103	1											
Income	-0.036	-0.016	0.135	-0.045	0.128	0.266	0.068	0.491	1										
Med	-0.035	-0.038	0.064	0.036	0.131	0.117	0.000	0.331	0.323	1									
Fed	0.125	-0.046	0.108	0.148	0.019	0.124	-0.034	0.224	0.476	0.486	1								
Career	-0.060	-0.089	0.038	0.194	-0.014	0.034	-0.262	0.166	0.118	0.088	0.179	1							
Risk	0.086	0.020	0.005	-0.067	0.327	0.149	0.072	0.090	-0.014	0.058	-0.023	0.110	1						
Cognitive	0.033	0.049	0.108	-0.017	0.041	0.109	0.014	0.083	0.040	0.169	-0.032	0.031	-0.115	1					
Extraversion	0.123	0.130	-0.029	0.112	0.199	0.290	-0.083	0.092	0.041	0.075	0.071	0.235	0.237	-0.116	1				
Agreeableness	0.011	0.069	0.124	0.267	0.029	-0.147	-0.267	0.029	-0.155	-0.006	-0.030	0.104	-0.046	-0.097	0.149	1			
Conscientiousness	0.153	0.120	0.289	0.369	0.166	-0.092	-0.319	0.008	0.013	0.026	0.137	0.199	0.170	-0.025	0.246	0.433	1		
Neuroticism	-0.025	0.039	0.079	0.020	-0.280	-0.173	0.170	-0.103	-0.156	-0.156	-0.143	0.015	-0.295	-0.006	-0.390	-0.063	-0.245	1	
Openness	0.016	0.013	0.083	0.042	0.054	-0.044	-0.085	-0.183	-0.023	-0.074	-0.003	0.172	0.192	-0.147	0.294	0.172	0.169	0.018	1

Figure B1. Personality Traits Density Distribution by Income

Table B2. Big Five Personality Traits and Grades: Income (OLS)

<i>y = academic grade</i>	(1)	(2)
Extraversion	- 0.612 (0.804)	- 1.050 (1.428)
Extraversion x High Income		0.501 (1.820)
Agreeableness	0.292 (0.781)	-0.485 (1.334)
Agreeableness x High Income		1.062 (1.737)
Conscientiousness	1.825** (2.202)	1.975 (1.279)
Conscientiousness x High Income		0.099 (1.744)
Neuroticism	1.520 * (0.798)	1.297 (1.236)
Neuroticism x High Income		0.417 (1.721)
Openness	0.453 (0.781)	1.124 (1.191)
Openness x High Income		-1.220 (1.591)
<i>N</i>	110	110
<i>R</i> ²	0.138	0.153
F-stat	2.328	1.330

*** denotes significance at the 1% level, ** at 5% and * at 10%. The Big Five variables have been standardised to have a mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1. All regressions control for age and income of the participant.